

NEURODYNAMICAL PREDICTION MODELS IN AUTOMATIC CONTROL SYSTEMS OF ENERGY FACILITIES

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Abstract. *Development of methods for nonlinear dynamic stochastic objects modeling based on neural networks technologies is considered. It is shown that neuro-emulators are suitable for the reconstruction of chaotic and stochastic characteristics in real time. Neural network methods and architecture for Hurst exponent reconstruction in real time is derived. The neural network architecture and control methods based on resonance filter in real time are derived. Recurrent neural network architecture and its training method are considered for real-time calculation of Hurst index.*

Keywords: *neuro-emulator, chaos dynamic reconstruction, Hurst exponent, identification, control systems.*

I. Methods of controlling parameters in energy objects.

The issues of controlling nonlinear dynamic objects in conditions of a priori and current uncertainty or external influences is one of the main issues of modern control theory. Such objects include, for example, energy systems, the movement of fluids in the boundary of turbulence, nonlinear optical devices, and various chemical reactions.

Classical control theory and adaptive systems theory methods for managing such objects are often ineffective. Because they are mainly based on object linearization system.

In this regard, methods based on computational intelligence: artificial neural networks (ANN), hybrid systems are increasingly used to solve control problems.

Neuroemulators and neuroregulators are the most common in tuning problems due to their universal approximation properties and the possibility of implementing nonlinear control laws. However, known artificial neural networks are usually based on the consideration of stochastic perturbation effects on the object. The characteristics of the change in the value of the technological parameters in energy facilities are considered as random processes. [1-3]

Many management objects in the field of energy cannot be described using the traditional models accepted in the identification theory. One of the main issues in control is that nonlinearity is not known a priori, its nature changes over time, and it is complicated by the appearance of gaps, vibration modes, and turbulence effects. Turbulent effects can also have a non-traditional stochastic character. [2-4]

Based on the mathematical model, the parameters in the control object are controlled. It will be possible to predict technological parameters with the help of constructed mathematical models. Determining the value of the parameters and determining the range of changes is the main part of the management issue. If the mathematical model is accurately constructed, the values of the output parameters in the control object are accurately predicted. This allows the production of quality raw materials or products in energy facilities.

II. Models of neuro-dynamic forecasting of parameters in energy objects.

Parameters are classically predicted by linear mathematical models. However, neurodynamic prediction allows to have accurate conclusions about the value of the parameter. In the neurodynamic method, several auxiliary quantities are calculated to predict the parameters.

The Hurst parameter is an exponent; therefore, the absolute or the relative deviation will heavily affect the modeling accuracy, necessitating their analysis. It is not just the overall variability of the errors that reflects the loss or risk in the model. Rarely occurring severe errors can be very much intolerable in some applications. Therefore, beyond the mean error values, we also calculate the 95% quantiles and the medians of the absolute and relative errors together with the maximum of the absolute error. The reason is that in real applications, we estimate the Hurst exponent trajectory-wise, and even if the estimation's significant inaccuracy occurs only in a small percentage of the observations. It still can cause unbearable loss or risk (Fig. 1). [10]

Figure 1. Neural network method to estimate the Hurst parameter.

Using the Hurst index, the following formula is used to determine the neural network of chaotic changes of parameters and to reconstruct the chaos.

$$R(k) = \max_{1 \leq i \leq k} x(i, k) - \min_{1 \leq i \leq k} x(i, k), \quad x(i, k) = \sum_{i=1}^k (y(i) - \bar{y}(i)) \quad (1)$$

$R(k)$ – dispersion of the sequence $x[n]$.

The recurrent neural network architecture and its training method for real-time calculation of the Hurst index are represented by the following equations.

$$\bar{S}(k) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{w} \sum_{i=k-w+1}^k (y(i) - \bar{y}(i))^2} \quad (2)$$

here h is an auxiliary variable, calculated using the relation.

The method of calculating the Hurst index for non-stationary objects is calculated using the following equation:

$$\frac{R(k)}{S(k)} = w^H \quad (3)$$

w – parametric deviation value; $\bar{R}(k)$ - the average value of the parametric deviation obtained according to the above ratio

$$\bar{S}(k) = \frac{1}{w} \sum_{i=k-w+1}^k S(i) \quad (4)$$

Hurst index is determined from equation (3) and (4).

$$H(k) = \log_w \frac{R(k)}{S(k)} \quad (5)$$

III. A neural network structure to predict the value of parameters

Based on the estimated complexity of the problem being solved, the author made attempts to synthesize neural networks. The number of internal layers of the neural network, increased the volume of the training sample, but all attempts at synthesis did not lead to the solution of the task. Initially, only transient process information was received at the ANN inputs. After analyzing the situation, it was decided to obtain the rate of its change as additional information about the transient process and thus feed not only the data of the transient processes, but also its first-order derivative to the ANN inputs. It was possible to synthesize a neural network that reproduces training and test sets. One of the stages of neural network synthesis was the simplification of its structure, while maintaining the high quality of ANN training and the ability to approximate previously unknown results for the neural network. Thus, in the course of the research, a partially connected (layered), forward-directed two-layer neural network with linear activation functions of neurons was synthesized (Fig. 2).

The inputs of the neural network receive the values of the ordinates of the reference points determined at the stage of formation of the training sample [4-7].

The general structure of the neural network is as follows:

$$NN \text{ IN} - H - OUT, \quad (2)$$

here NN – is the neural network, IN (input) – is the number of input neurons, H (hidden) – is the number of neurons in the hidden layer, OUT (output) – are the identifiable parameters of the regulated object. [4-8]

Figure. 2. The structure of the neural network for identifying the parameters of the regulated object.

The number of neurons in the input layer of the ANN is equal to the amount of data for training the neural network.

$$IN = n.$$

The number of neurons in the hidden layer is equal to half of the neurons in the input layer, because the neuron of the hidden layer receives information on the ordinates of the reference points at the current time from the transient process and the impulse response. [8]

The number of outputs of the identification neural network is determined by the type of the applied transfer function of the regulated object.

Conclusion. In this research, the interrelationship between the parameters of energy objects is considered. A neurodynamic method for predicting parameters is considered. Auxiliary parameters are introduced for neurodynamic analysis. A neural network system is selected depending on the auxiliary parameter value. A neural network structure is introduced to predict the value of the output parameters. A three-layer neural network was used for the problem of neurodynamic forecasting.

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